

**LARVICIDAL ACTIVITIES OF *CARICA PAPAYA* LINN
(CARICACEAE) LATEX GEL ON LARVAE OF *AEDES AEGYTI* IN
DENGUE VECTOR CONTROL IN LOKOSSA DISTRICT IN SOUTH-
WESTERN REPUBLIC OF BENIN, WEST AFRICA**

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ABSTRACT

Background: Mosquito control programs are now threatened by the selection of mosquito populations resistant to the chemical insecticides. Thus, alternative vector control methods are necessary. **Objective:** This study was aimed at investigating on the larvicidal activities of *Carica papaya* Linn latex gel on larvae of *Aedes aegyti* in dengue vector control in Lokossa district in south-western Republic of Benin, West Africa. **Methodology:** Larvae of *Aedes aegyti* mosquitoes were collected from breeding sites using the dipping method from September to November 2024 during the small rainy season in Lokossa district. A batch of 25 larvae of fourth instar were exposed to a mixture of *Carica papaya* Linn latex gel containing in each of five glass jars or test cups of same dimensions with different concentrations of 1mg/l, 2mg/l, 3mg/l, 4mg/l and 5mg/l and one control jar for each serial concentrations containing no trace of *Carica papaya* Linn latex gel. Larval mortality was recorded after 24 hours, 48 hours and 72hours exposure. **Results:** The results showed that *Carica*

papaya Linn latex gel had acted by poisoning the larvae of four instars which could not

breathe and pupate. **Conclusion:** The use of *Carica papaya* Linn latex gel disallows mosquito larvae to acquire tolerance.

KEYWORDS: *Carica papaya* latex gel, siphonal respiration, *Aedes aegypti*, dengue, Republic of Benin.

INTRODUCTION

Insects, the most abundant and important group of organisms in the world found almost everywhere and able to thrive where others are absent transmit diseases that induce an enormous burden on the world's population.^[1,2] Mosquitoes, a group of insect transmit diseases than any other insect group and are well known vectors for most life threatening diseases affecting millions of people around the world such as malaria, Dengue fever, Lymphatic filariasis, Yellow fever, Japanese encephalitis, La Cross fever, Chikungunya fever.^[3,4,5,6,7,8]

Dengue is the most important vector-borne infectious disease in the world. It is estimated that more than 50 million infections occur and half a million individuals are hospitalized due to dengue hemorrhagic fever each year. The infection is caused by one of four dengue virus serotypes: DENV-1, DENV-2, DENV-3, or DENV-4.^[9,10] The *Aedes* mosquito is the primary vector for the transmission of dengue fever. A successful integrated mosquito control strategy includes several tactics, such as removing mosquito breeding sites and using synthetic chemical insecticides (pyrethroids, organophosphates, etc.) to control the spread of adult or larval forms of *Aedes aegypti*.^[11]

While synthetic chemicals have successfully controlled *Aedes* mosquito populations, the tremendous increase in their use has led to insecticide resistance in mosquito vectors^[12] and adverse effects on non-target organisms, including humans.^[13] Therefore, developing safe and eco-friendly insecticides is important for public health.

Botanicals have a wide spread insecticidal properties and are obviously suggestive of a new weapon in the arsenal of insecticides and in future may act as a suitable alternative product to fight against mosquito borne diseases.^[14,15] The secondary metabolites present in these botanicals constitute a defense system against insect pest attacks; their presence has been held responsible for the biological activity of plant extracts against target pests. The use of plant-derived natural products as larvicides have the advantage of being harmless to beneficial non-

target organisms and the environment when compared to synthetic ones.^[16] The efficacy of phytochemicals against the mosquito species have been shown to vary significantly depending on plant species, plant parts used, the nature of the plant (young, adult or senescent), a solvent used for extraction and the species of mosquito tested. These differential responses have been influenced by extrinsic and intrinsic factors such as the geographical location of the plant and mosquito species, plant parts used, extraction methodology adopted, the polarity of the solvent used during extraction.^[17-20,21-22]

Latex was a fluid secreted by laticifer cells in plants. The biological role of latex secretion in plants remains unknown, but several types of research proved that it has insecticidal property.^[23] Latex contains highly active chemicals such as aromatics, terpenoids, alkaloids, phenols, glycosides, carbohydrates and proteins.^[24] Further, in ancient time, latex was practiced in traditional and folk medicine for treating ailments and diseases.

Very few researches were published on the use of essential oils in *Aedes aegypti* larvae tolerance in Benin. Therefore, there is a need to carry out new researches for this purpose.

The goal of this study was to investigate on the larvicidal activities of *Carica papaya* Linn (Caricaceae) latex gel on larvae of *Aedes aegypti* in dengue vector control in Lokossa district in south-western Republic of Benin, West Africa.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study area

The study area is located in Republic of Benin (West Africa) and includes the department of Mono. Mono department is located in the south-western Republic of Benin and the study was carried out more precisely in Lokossa district (Fig. 1). The southern borders of this district are Athiémé and Houéyogbé districts. The northern border is Dogbo district. The eastern border is Bopa district and the western border is Togo republic. Lokossa district covered 260 km². The choice of the study sites took into account the economic activities of populations, their usual protection practices against mosquito bites and peasant practices to control farming pests. We took these factors into account to study the larvicidal activities of *Carica papaya* Linn latex gel on larvae of *Aedes aegypti* in dengue vector control in Lokossa district. Lokossa has a climate with four seasons, two rainy seasons (March-July and August-November) and two dry seasons (November-March and July-August). The temperature ranged from 25 to 32°C with the annual mean rainfall, which is between 900 and 1100 mm.

Fig. 1: Map of Republic of Benin showing Lokossa District Surveyed.

Mosquito sampling

Aedes aegypti larvae were collected from September to November 2024 during the small rainy season in Lokossa district. Larvae were collected from breeding sites using the dipping method and kept in labeled bottles. Adult *Aedes aegypti* from these breeding sites were previously identified. The samples were then carried out to the Laboratory of Pluridisciplinary Researches of Technical Teaching (LaRPET) in the Department of Sciences and Agricultural Techniques located in Dogbo district.

Latex collection

Latex gel was collected in sterile bottles from unripe mature fruits on paw paw (Fig. 2) in Lokossa district. For that, unripe mature fruits were pierced with needles and latex gel was taken in the sterile bottles. Then, these bottles were carried out to Laboratory of Pluridisciplinary Researches of Technical Teaching (LaRPET) for bioassays.

Fig. 2: *Carica papaya* tree.

Bioassays

A batch of twenty five (25) larvae of fourth instar reared in the insectary of the Department of Sciences and Agricultural Techniques was added to each of five glass jars or test cups of same dimensions containing the dilutions of 1.0mg/liter, 2.0mg/liter, 3.0mg/liter, 4.0 mg/liter and 5.0mg/liter respectively of *Carica papaya* Linn latex gel. These tests cup were covered with small cutting untreated net. At each range of dilutions, there is a corresponding control. The control jars contained no trace of *Carica papaya* Linn latex gel.

Four replicates were set up and an equal number of controls were set up simultaneously with distilled water. The test containers were held at 25-28°C.

Larval mortality was recorded after 24hours, 48hours and 72hours exposure. Dead larvae were those that could not be induced to move when they were probed with a needle in the siphon or the cervical region. Moribund larvae were those incapable of rising to the surface or not showing the characteristic diving reaction when the water was disturbed.

Statistical analysis

Analysis using t-test was performed with 95% confidence interval in SPSS version 16.0 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL). The p-value acquired by t-test for all cases of this study is less than 5%.

RESULTS

Evaluation of larvicidal effect of *Carica papaya* latex gel on larvae of *Aedes aegypti* from Lokossa district

The analysis of figure 3 showed that after the exposure of *Aedes aegypti* larvae of fourth instar (L4) to *Carica papaya* Linn latex gel, no dead and moribund larvae were registered in the control plastic cups after 24 hours, 48 hours and 72 hours recording, they were all alive. The analysis of the same figure showed that very few dead larvae were registered after 24 hours exposure with all tested concentrations of 1mg/l, 2mg/l, 3 mg/l, 4mg/l and 5mg/l ($P > 0,05$). The recording of 48 hours exposure showed that dead larvae were registered in the all test plastic cups with all tested concentrations of 1mg/l, 2mg/l, 3 mg/l, 4mg/l and 5mg/l ($P < 0,05$). The number of dead larvae recorded after 48 hours exposure was higher than that registered after 24 hours exposure. The recording of 72 hours exposure showed that more dead larvae were registered in the all test plastic cups with all tested concentrations of 1mg/l, 2mg/l, 3 mg/l, 4mg/l and 5mg/l ($P < 0,05$). Otherwise, the number of dead larvae recorded after 72 hours exposure was higher than that registered after 48 hours exposure. Finally, the highest mortality rate was recorded with the concentration of 5 mg/l (80 dead larvae on a total of 125 tested larvae).

Fig. 3: Larvicidal activity of *Carica papaya* latex gel against *Aedes aegypti* larvae.

Advantages and disadvantages of the use of *Carica papaya* latex gel against *Aedes aegypti* larvae

The analysis of Table 1 shows that there are many advantages in the use of *Carica papaya* latex gel to control mosquito larvae. But, also there are very few disadvantages.

Table 1: Advantages and disadvantages of the use of *Carica papaya* latex gel.

Advantages	Disadvantages
<p><i>Carica papaya</i> tree (paw paw) is cultivated in many regions in Benin country</p> <p><i>Carica papaya</i> latex gel is a cheap and easy method of larval control for some breeding sites such as borrow-pits, pools and so on</p> <p>Mosquitoes may not develop resistance to <i>Carica papaya</i> latex gel</p>	<p>Limited effectiveness of <i>Carica papaya</i> latex gel in the presence of vegetation and floating debris (is the main disadvantage)</p>
<p><i>Carica papaya</i> latex gel is not toxic to most non-target organisms including mammals and fish.</p>	
<p><i>Carica papaya</i> latex gel cannot soil the earth after its action or effect where it has been applied</p>	

DISCUSSION

In the current study, after the exposure of *Aedes aegypti* larvae of fourth instar (L4) to *Carica papaya* Linn latex gel, no dead and moribund larvae were registered in the control plastic cups after 24 hours, 48 hours and 72 hours recording, they were all alive. Very few dead larvae were registered after 24 hours exposure with all tested concentrations of 1mg/l, 2mg/l, 3 mg/l, 4mg/l and 5mg/l. The 48 hours exposure showed that dead larvae were registered in the all test plastic cups with all tested concentrations of 1mg/l, 2mg/l, 3 mg/l, 4mg/l and 5mg/l. The number of dead larvae recorded after 48 hours exposure was higher than that registered after 24 hours exposure. The 72 hours exposure showed that more dead larvae were registered in the all test plastic cups with all tested concentrations of 1mg/l, 2mg/l, 3 mg/l, 4mg/l and 5mg/l. Otherwise, the number of dead larvae recorded after 72 hours exposure was higher than that registered after 48 hours exposure. Finally, the highest mortality rate was recorded with the concentration of 5 mg/l. These results showed that the use of *Carica papaya* latex gel causes full-grown *Aedes aegypti* larvae to die by suffocation. After the application of *Carica papaya* latex gel, the larvae of fourth instar cannot breathe. Our results corroborated with those obtained by Kuberan *et al*^[25] who had studied the larvicidal efficacy of *Carica papaya* latex extract and silver nanoparticles (CPAgNPs) synthesized using latex, against developing immature juveniles of *Aedes aegypti*. Briefly, the latex was collected and fractioned with different solvents such as chloroform, methanol and

aqueously. The obtained crude extracts were subjected to larvicidal activity in the dose-dependent method. After 24 hours, the mortality rate was calculated and statistically analyzed. From their results, it was demonstrated that the chloroform extract displayed prominent activity in IInd and IIIrd instar larvae of *Aedes aegypti* with better LC₅₀ values followed by methanol and aqueous extract. Subsequently, they profiled the qualitative analysis of a chloroform extract through biochemical tests; Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy and gas chromatography-mass spectrometry. Moreover, they authenticated the major secondary metabolites and activated larvicidal compound present in the extract. Further, they synthesized CPAgNPs using aqueous latex extract and challenged with IInd and IIIrd instar larvae of *Aedes aegypti*. Noticeably, the synthesized nanoproducts were showed 100% mortality in a 24 hours treatment with significant LC₅₀ values. Hence, their study has opened up new vistas in the field of parasitological research to develop *Carica papaya* latex as a new stratagem in the insect vector management program.

Another research carried out by Kovendan *et al* ^[26] had studied the bioefficacy of larvicidal and pupicidal properties of *Carica papaya* (Caricaceae) leaf extract and bacterial insecticide, spinosad, against chikungunya vector, *Aedes aegypti* (Diptera: Culicidae). For that, the larvicidal activity of *Carica papaya*, crude extracts of the plant have been tested such as crude methanol extract of the leaf of *Carica papaya* and showed highest activity against the first and fourth instar of *Aedes aegypti* with LC₅₀ values of 51.76ppm and 82.18ppm and pupae was 440.65ppm.

CONCLUSION

The use of *Carica papaya* latex gel is effective on larvae of fourth instar of *Aedes aegypti* in the current study. *Carica papaya* latex gel can help for new stratagem in the control of mosquito larvae in vector management program. Also, the bio-active molecules responsible of larvae mortality or lethality and their mode of actions remain indistinct and imprecise, and this calls for further pharmacological and clinical research on them.

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